

Triangulation of a Triangle with Triangles having Equal Inscribed Circles

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In this article, we solve the following problem:

Any triangle can be divided by a cevian in two triangles that have congruent inscribed circles.

Solution

We consider a given triangle ABC and we show that there is a point D on the side (BC) so that the inscribed circles in the triangles ABD , ACD are congruent. If ABC is an isosceles triangle ($AB = AC$), where D is the middle of the base (BC) , we assume that ABC is a non-isosceles triangle.

We note I_1, I_2 the centers of the inscribed congruent circles; obviously, I_1I_2 is parallel to the BC (1).

We observe that $m(\sphericalangle I_1AI_2) = \frac{1}{2}m(\hat{A})$ (2).

Fig. 1

If T_1, T_2 are contacts with the circles of the cevian AD , we have $\Delta I_1 T_1 M \equiv \Delta I_2 T_2 M$; let M be the intersection of $I_1 I_2$ with AD , see *Fig. 1*.

From this congruence, it is obvious that $(I_1 M) \equiv (I_2 M)$ (3).

Let I be the center of the circle inscribed in the triangle ABC ; we prove that: **AI is a simedian in the triangle $I_1 A I_2$** (4).

Indeed, noting $\alpha = m(\widehat{BAI_1})$, it follows that $m(\sphericalangle I_1 A M) = \alpha$. From $\sphericalangle I_1 A I_2 = \sphericalangle B A I$, it follows that $\sphericalangle B A I_1 \equiv \sphericalangle I A I_2$, therefore $\sphericalangle I_1 A M \equiv \sphericalangle I A I_2$, indicating that AM and AI are isogonal cevians in the triangle $I_1 A I_2$. Since in this triangle AM is a median, it follows that AI is a simedian.

Now, we show how we build the point D , using the conditions (1) – (4), and then we prove that this construction satisfies the enunciation requirements.

Building the point D

1⁰: We build the circumscribed circle of the given triangle ABC ; we build the bisector of the angle BAC and denote by P its intersection with the circumscribed circle (see *Fig. 2*).

2⁰: We build the perpendicular on C to CP and (BC) side mediator; we denote O_1 the intersection of these lines.

3⁰: We build the circle $C(O_1; O_1 C)$ and denote A' the intersection of this circle with the bisector AI (A' is on the same side of the line BC as A).

4⁰: We build through A the parallel to $A'O_1$ and we denote it IO_1 .

5⁰: We build the circle $C(O'_1; O'_1 A)$ and we denote I_1, I_2 its intersections with BI , and CI respectively.

6⁰: We build the middle M of the segment (I_1I_2) and denote by D the intersection of the lines AM and BC .

Fig. 2

Proof

The point P is the middle of the arc $\widehat{BC}$, then $m(\widehat{PCB}) = \frac{1}{2}m(\hat{A})$.

The circle $C(O_1; O_1C)$ contains the arc from which points the segment (BC) „is shown” under angle measurement $\frac{1}{2}m(\hat{A})$.

The circle $C(O'_1; O'_1A)$ is homothetical to the circle $C(O_1; O_1C)$ by the homothety of center I and by the report $\frac{IA'}{IA}$; therefore, it follows that I_1I_2 will be parallel to the BC , and from the points of circle $C(O'_1; O'_1A)$ of the same side of BC as A , the segment (I_1I_2) „is shown” at an angle of measure $\frac{1}{2}m(\hat{A})$. Since the tangents taken in B and C to the circle $C(O_1; O_1C)$

intersect in P , on the bisector AI , as from a property of simedians, we get that $A'I$ is a simedian in the triangle $A'BC$. Due to the homothetical properties, it follows also that the tangents in the points I_1, I_2 to the circle $C(O'_1; O'_1A)$ intersect in a point P' located on AI , i.e. AP' contains the simedian (AS) of the triangle I_1AI_2 , noted $\{S\} = AP' \cap I_1I_2$. In the triangle I_1AI_2 , AM is a median, and AS is simedian, therefore $\sphericalangle I_1AM \equiv I_2AS$; on the other hand, $\sphericalangle BAS \equiv \sphericalangle I_1AI_2$; it follows that $\sphericalangle BAI_1 \equiv I_2AS$, and more: $\sphericalangle I_1AM \equiv BAI_1$, which shows that AI_1 is a bisector in the triangle BAD ; plus, I_1 , being located on the bisector of the angle B , it follows that this point is the center of the circle inscribed in the triangle BAD . Analogous considerations lead to the conclusion that I_2 is the center of the circle inscribed in the triangle ACD . Because I_1I_2 is parallel to BC , it follows that the rays of the circles inscribed in the triangles ABD and ACD are equal.

Discussion

The circles $C(O_1; O_1A')$, $C(O'_1; O'_1A)$ are unique; also, the triangle I_1AI_2 is unique; therefore, determined as before, the point D is unique.

Remark

At the beginning of the *Proof*, we assumed that ABC is a non-isosceles triangle with the stated property. There exists such triangles; we can construct such a triangle starting "backwards". We consider two given congruent external circles and, by tangent constructions, we highlight the ABC triangle.

Open problem

Given a scalene triangle ABC , could it be triangulated by the cevians AD, AE , with D, E belonging to (BC) , so that the inscribed circles in the triangles ABD, DAE and the EAC to be congruent?